

ORGAN TRANSPLANT

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Annotation: The development of oncological diseases and their sharp increase, the path to dignity in the medical field.

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Oncology and its consequences

Oncology is a branch of medicine that studies benign and malignant tumors, the mechanisms and patterns of their occurrence and development, and methods for their prevention, diagnosis and treatment. Cancer is a broad and heterogeneous class of diseases. Oncological diseases are systemic and affect, in one way or another, all human organs and systems. There are many forms and variants of the course of cancer. Although patients often perceive an oncological diagnosis as a death sentence, not all, even malignant, tumors lead to death. Modern studies have shown that cancer cells and microtumors regularly appear in every person in the body, which die and resolve under the influence of the antitumor immunity system.

Cancer cells spread by entering the bloodstream or lymphatic system. The lymphatic system is a series of small vessels that carry a fluid called lymph. The lymph collects "waste" from the cells, transfers them to the lymph nodes, where they are already filtered out. Then there is an outflow of lymph into the blood. Each year, the cancer virus spreads widely across the field, with humans going through four stages. The cancerous growth is rapidly growing and cannot be stopped, although it can be stopped in English. These grow rapidly and are important because they contain a lot of extracellular and intracellular mucus. The latter pushes the nucleus against the cell wall, which makes the cell look like a ring. Ring-shaped modes of transport are provided below others. phenomena of tumor thickening and rise, subcutaneous nodes. This is especially true for the area of the mammary glands, inguinal glands, and armpits. Blood or pus, sometimes mucus, may appear in the urine and stool. Wounds are not observed for a long time, coughing may not go away for a long time, the timbre of the voice is observed. Cancer cells spread by entering the bloodstream or lymphatic system. The lymphatic system is a series of small vessels that carry a fluid called

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Reduced efficiency, constant feeling of discomfort, fatigue, decreased interest in the surrounding reality, causeless. Tissue growth. If during a visual examination or palpation, you find a deformation or asymmetry of some part of the body, you should pay special attention to this. Oncology has several types, but the most common type is considered to be gynecological oncology. All over the world, gynecological oncology is considered a dangerous disease, which is in second place in terms of its ability to spread.

Oncogynecology is a branch of medicine located at the intersection of oncology, gynecology, urology, and endocrinology and studying benign and malignant tumors of the female reproductive system (labia, vagina, vulva, cervix, uterus and fallopian tubes, ovaries, mammary glands), their etiology, pathogenesis, methods of their prevention, diagnosis and treatment (surgical, radiation, chemotherapeutic and hormonal). The subject of oncogynecology includes, in particular, vaginal cancer, cervical cancer, endometrial carcinoma, ovarian cancer, breast cancer, and vulvar cancer. Many people are convinced that such a disease did not exist before. People have never had this disease before. But everything is not so simple. Malignant tumors have accompanied man for many centuries. Their descriptions are found in some historical documents. The first written mention of this disease and its treatment is found in the papyri of ancient Egypt, dating back to 1600 BC. These documents mention some types of breast cancer and methods of healing them, consisting of the cauterization of the affected tissues. For the treatment of skin tumors, cauterizing ointments were used, which contained arsenic. Similar descriptions are found in the Ramayana (an ancient Indian epic). The epic tells that the treatment consisted of ointments with arsenic, and also included the surgical removal of the tumor. For the first time, this disease was called "cancer" by Hippocrates, the legendary ancient Greek healer. "Carcinoma" is translated from Greek as "cancer", as it looked like a crab with outgrowths that spread out in different directions. The doctor also suggested the term "onkos". In his notes, he describes in detail breast, gastrointestinal, skin, cervical, rectal, and nasopharyngeal cancers. He offered to treat these "carcinomas" only surgically. To do this, it is enough to remove accessible bad formations and further disinfect wounds-ointments with plant poisons and arsenic. Such a composition, according to the healer, should kill the remaining particles (cells) of this "crab". In the presence of tumors, the legendary Hippocrates does nothing at all, since performing a complex operation kills the patient faster than the "crab" itself.

These days, professionals say that the spread of cancer has increased by 2.5% on average in the last century, and this speaks to a two-in-ten chance of encountering a cancer virus. The modern disease associated with the spread of cancer, the transplantation of an affected organ into a charged place in front of that virus, which is on a process that does not spread through the blood to the whole body, concerns the coverage of the whole organism. This method is mainly developed in the second and stage stages, before moving to the fourth stage. According to oncologists, a person does not recognize the first stage of this disease, because the first stage can pass without symptoms or pain in the onset of symptoms. It is even impossible to detect this when a person has contracted the virus, since the oncological virus can hide for more than ten years, without affecting the surrounding people.

In 2020, 19.3 million new cases of the disease were detected in the world, and about 10 million people died from the formidable disease. More than 20 cases of cancer are detected annually in Uzbekistan, while the number of oncological diseases in the republic is more than 100,000. Uzbekistan has begun to put methods of treatment and spread of this virus in order to reduce the mortality rate for this item. The country has started serum treatment in adolescents, especially in the period of nongynecological diseases. In line with this, the construction of oncological dispensaries increased for each area of education in the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology, the Center for Cancer Prevention, and the Center for Experimental Oncology, without the formation of legal entities, within the general concentration of personnel;

transformation of territorial oncological dispensaries and the Tashkent City Oncological Dispensary into branches of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Oncological Center and Radiology. study of modern methods of diagnosis, diagnosis, and treatment of oncological diseases with the involvement of highly qualified medical and preventive care for the population in the field of oncology;

Collection of scientific and practical research and research in the field of oncology, including the use of advanced achievements in the field of prevention and early diagnosis of oncological diseases, the phased application of screening programs for early oncological disease;

increasing the level of provision of oncological institutions with medicines, reagents, and consumables;

modernization of the material and technical base of a new oncological structure based on their structure, structure and overhaul, increasing (retrofitting) the mass, tools and inventory; modern medical science.

advanced training of personnel of oncological institutions and expansion of domestic scientific research in the field of prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of oncological diseases. Additional lessons in human history have been added and books on cancer have been published.

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